

Fig. S1: NW-SE hydrographic-seismic intersection across the Great South Basin. The colour gradient represents salinity variations (in PSU). The water masses comprise: STW – Subtropical Water, SAW – Sub-Antarctic Water, SAMW – Sub-Antarctic Mode Water, AAIW – Antarctic Intermediate Water, and TZ – transition zone between SAMW and AAIW.

Fig. S2: Uninterpreted and interpreted section of a seismic profile running along the Toroa and Tara wells showing the correlation between the main discontinuities (R1, R3, R4, R5, and R6). This seismic profile is also shown in Figure 3B. The scatter diagram shows the time-depth data for these wells, and the trend line (red dashed line) used to depth-convert the data.

Seismic facies for mixed/hybrid depositional systems

Types	seismic section	line drawing	internal configuration and shape	Distribution and seismic units
Major features	Depositional mound SW NE 0.1KM 0.2s 	 draping onlap	low - moderate amplitude parallel to sub-parallel continuous progradation-aggradational reflections with a heightened convex-upward steeply dipping SW flank (crest) and a gently dipping NE flank asymmetric concave-shape with smooth NE flank and steep SW flank	middle continental slope of U1 and U2 downslope elongated mound
	Mixed levee-drift SW NE 0.1KM 0.2s 	 Toplap onlap and downlap	concave-up high amplitude reflection separated occasionally by chaotic reflections overlain by low amplitude sigmoid-shape reflections wedge shape	middle continental slope of U1 and U2 1 downslope elongated mound 2 hybrid levee-drift 3 channel lag
	Mixed levee-drift SW NE 0.1KM 0.2s 	 onlap	high amplitude reflections laterally extending into drifts Channel lag and draping onlap	middle continental slope of U1
	Erosional Channel SW NE 0.1KM 0.2s 	 onlap bank? downlap	high amplitude basal reflection with adjacent downlapping reflections truncating against it. convex-up geometry is later filled by onlapping reflections: note wedging reflection downlapping channel wall and fault underlying the channel convex U-shape channel-onlap fill	middle continental slope of U1
Secondary features	Depositional Plastered drift NW SE 0.1KM 0.2s 	 Toplap	moderate to high amplitude parallel, continuous aggradational reflections plastered or sheet like external shape with erosional top	middle continental slope of U2 1 Plastered drift
	Depositional Sediment waves NW SE 0.1KM 0.2s 	 onlap	variable amplitude of low-moderate-high asymmetric wavefield stacked aggradationally. This reflection pattern has a short and thick wavelength upslope in the NW compared with the thin and longer wavelength downslope in the SW tabular or sheet external shape	middle to lower continental slope of U2 sediment waves
Major features	Erosional Channel SW NE 0.1KM 0.2s 	 concordant onlap	high amplitude erosive reflection overlain by chaotic to transparent reflections infilling basal surface. The channel infill is capped by moderate to high amplitude laterally continuous sub-parallel reflections convex U-shape Channel-chaotic fill	middle continental slope of U1 and U2 1 MTDs 2 Channel basal lag
	Erosional Channel SW NE 0.1KM 0.2s 	 onlap	semi-parallel high amplitude reflections onlapping against the flank of the channel incision. Reflections grade laterally into moderate amplitudes to the NE truncating against a local normal fault. The truncation towards the SW is in the form of a stratigraphic wedge convex U-shape channel-onlap fill	middle continental slope of U1 and U2
Secondary features	Others Top of Mound SW NE 0.2s 0.1KM 	 Toplap	low amplitude continuous reflections overlain by variable amplitude discontinuous disrupted by layer bound arrays of fault and finally capped by high amplitude discontinuous to chaotic reflections exhibiting toplap truncation with overlying surface	middle continental slope of U1
	Mixed Contourite terrace NW SE 0.1KM 0.2s 	 onlap	moderate amplitude oblique to sigmoid reflections exhibiting erosional or toplap truncation against an overlying flat surface to the southeast while downlap termination against the underlying reflection to the northwest. widespread sheet	upper and middle continental slope of U4

Fig. S3: Seismic facies scheme devised for interpretation of depositional environments in this study.

Table S1: Details of the main 2D seismic acquisition parameters for the Great South Basin

Dataset	OMV-08	OMV-10	DUN-06	GSB 2D	GP 10
Year	2008	2010	2006	2008	2010
Research vessel	RV Discoverer	MV Reflect	M/V Pacific titan	Western Trident	RV Resolution
No of lines	123	63	23	23	17
Streamer length (km)	6	8	6	6	6
Source	Air guns	Air guns	Air Guns	Air guns	Air guns
Shot interval (m)	25	25	25	25	25
Group interval (m)	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5	12.5
No of group	480	640	480	480	480
Record length (s)	8	8.2	8	8	8
Sample rate (ms)	2	2	2	2	2
Data recorded by:	Seabed Exploration Ltd	Reflect Geophysical Pte. Ltd	Multiwave Geophysical Company	Western Geco (Schlumberger)	Key Seismic Solutions Ltd, 2010
Reference	(Seabed Exploration Ltd, 2008)	(Reflect Geophysical Pte Ltd, 2010)	(Multiwave Geophysical Company, 2006)	(WesternGeco Schlumberger company, 2008)	(Key Seismic Solutions Ltd, 2010)

Table S2: Regional stratigraphic discontinuities defined by Constable et al. (2013), Cook (1999), Omosanya and Harishidayat (2019) and McMillan and Wilson (1997) for the Great South Basin, New Zealand continental margin.

Constable et al. (2013)		Cook et al. (1999)		Omosanya and Harishidayat (2019)		McMillan and Wilson (1997)	
Regional age discontinuity	Attributed age	Regional age discontinuity	Attributed age	Regional age discontinuity	Attributed age	Regional age discontinuity	Attributed age
Seafloor	Holocene	Seafloor	Holocene	H14	Holocene	NA	NA
T100		NA				NA	NA
T90	Mid-Miocene	NA	Mid-Miocene	H13	Mid-Miocene	NA	NA
T80	Mid-Oligocene	NA	Mid-Oligocene	H12	Mid-Oligocene	UC11	Mid-Oligocene
T70	Late Eocene	Dark Blue	Late Eocene	H11	Late Eocene	UC9	Late Eocene
T50	Mid-Eocene	NA	Mid-Eocene	H8	Mid-Eocene	NA	NA

Table S3: Summary of the bounding discontinuities, seismic units and reflection termination patterns.

seismic characteristics of the main seismic units U1-U4 and their discontinuities R6-R1

Seismic Units	Age	Seismic discontinuities	Reflection termination	internal configuration and shape	
				shelf	slope
U4	12-0 Ma	R4 High amplitude positive reflection continuous at regional scale	toplap/truncation 	low to moderate amplitude sigmoid reflections, elongated lens	low to high amplitude subparallel continuous reflections, aggradational sheets
		High amplitude positive reflection, laterally continuous reflections	downlap/onlap 		
U3	27-12 Ma	R3	toplap/truncation 	low to moderate amplitude subparallel to divergent reflections, aggradational sheet	low to high amplitude subparallel continuous reflections, aggradational sheets
		Moderate to high amplitude negative reflection, laterally continuous at basin scale	downlap/onlap 		
U2	33.7-27 Ma	R4	onlap 	low to moderate amplitude subparallel to divergent and occasionally chaotic reflections, aggradational sheet	moderate amplitude continuous reflections, aggradational sheet
		High amplitude positive reflection erosive, continuous at regional scale			
U1	45-33.7 Ma	R5	toplap/truncation 	low to moderate amplitude subparallel to divergent and occasionally chaotic reflections, aggradational sheet	low to moderate amplitude change vertically into high amplitude reflection as aggradational sheet change laterally into moderate amplitude reflections and elongated mounds
		Low to moderate amplitude negative reflection continuous at regional scale	downlap/onlap 		
		R6			

Supplementary References

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